

D4.4

Digital touchpoints design and implementation

Public Deliverable

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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Delivery Deadline	Actual delivery
1	Submission of Internal Draft Deliverable to reviewers	26/11/2019	27/11/2019
2	Initial Review and Comments obtained	29/11/2019	29/11/2019
3	Uploading of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal and submission	30/11/2019	30/11/2019

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 4.4 “Digital touchpoints design, implementation, and test” comes as the closure of WP4 “Free Wheel service and digital touchpoints design”. With the declared intent of delivering a full mobile app experience, we developed an Android App that is the first and only touchpoint the Customer is going to interact with, collecting data and exchanging them with the cloud-based FreeWheel ecosystem to enable the service delivery team to deal with operations.

The App features set covers all the Customer experience’s phases described in the Service Blueprint (D4.2): gearing up (service suitability check, registration, assistance to adaptor design, production delivery and installation), booking (in advance or on-the-fly), running service (identifying, attaching, and detaching the module) and wrapping up (detaching the module, paying).

The App implementation followed the timing described in the previous Deliverable 4.3 “Service implementation roadmap” and every feature was developed accordingly to the forecasted statuses that the collaborative work highlighted, concerning all related to the mobile App this deliverable is about.

The development started with the design of the app experience thanks to the Service Blueprint, together with the development, with frequent collaboration with all the partners, especially the ones involved in WP3 tasks, to better shape the connection between all the technologies that are enabling the FreeWheel service.

The operations to achieve the deliverable, run in coordination with an iterative approach, were:

- User Experience Design: interaction design, wireframing, prototyping and visual design of the app
- DevOps: Back-End and Front-End development
- Code testing and validation

The results of these operations are:

- Android APK, an installable package for Android-based smartphones
- Back-End package, that communicates with the Android App to deliver support processes

They are available for download at this web address:

<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1Uuzpwlrk7Ekv2K6uOEKzi7zlfJguMVN/view?usp=sharing>

In order to ensure safety, **these files are shared only to authorized who request access**. The request can be made just clicking on the link, **please note that there is a delay** between request and authorization due to a quick authorization check made by a project officer.

In addition, please remember that these applications are prototypes intended to deliver the experience during the final demonstrator, so we strongly suggest not install and test them in any circumstance right now. Even if they are fully functional, they need some preparative operations to work properly and deliver the correct experience in the context of the FreeWheel research project.

This is why this document is here to describe both the process resumed in the lines above and how the app is going to deliver the service accordingly to the work done so far (Service Blueprint D4.2).

Technical content

1. Development

1.1. Tech specs

The development activities are based on a proper technical specifications document. All the technical specifications, figured out starting from requirements, objectives, and challenges, outline the whole system in terms of logic, performance and third party solutions' integration.

Below, a high-level system architecture is shown in order to describe each functional block through the tech specs' subset that has driven its development.

1.2. System architecture

1.3. Mobile client app

The mobile client app is the touchpoint between the Customer base and the whole system. It is a mobile Android application that has been developed in a native environment. Developing in a native Android environment permits lower-level access to the operative system networking API, and so, a more secure and robust Bluetooth and TCP communication management.

The mobile app can communicate with module controller units through a Bluetooth connection. At the same time, all data communication between the mobile client, the back-end component and other third party services over the web, is among TCP secure connections.

1.4. Mobile controller unit

The mobile controller is composed of the following parts: an onboard controller, a Bluetooth network interface, a GPIO interface, and all the hardware needed to physically move the wheelchair (engines, joysticks, brakes, sensors...).

The onboard controller is a LattePanda microcomputer and can operate as a hardware controller and data processor for all the control data coming from the mobile application and sensors or going to engines and other controlled hardware components.

Below are outlined the microcomputer technical specifications:

- CPU : Intel 8th m3--8100y
- Core : 1.1-3.4GHz Dual-Core, Four-Thread
- Benchmark (PassMark): Up to 4128, double computing power compared with same price range products in the market
- Graphics : Intel HD Graphics 615, 300-900MHz
- RAM : 8G LPDDR3
- eMMC: 64GB
- External Memory :
 - o 1x M.2 M Key, PCIe 4x, Supports NVMe SSD and SATA SSD
 - o 1x M.2 E Key, PCIe 2x, Supports USB2.0, UART, PCM
- Connectivity : WIFI 802.11 AC, 2.4G & 5G
- Dual-Band Bluetooth 4.2
- Gigabyte Ethernet
- USB Ports : 3x USB 3.0 Type-A / 1x USB Type C, supports PD, DP, USB 3.0
- Display : HDMI Output / Type-C DP Support / Extendable eDP touch displays
- Co-processor : Arduino Leonardo
- GPIO & Other Features : 2x 50p GPIOs including I2C, I2S, USB, RS232, UART, RTC, Power Management, Extendable power button, everything you need
- OS Support : Windows 10 Pro / Linux Ubuntu
- Dimension: 115mm * 78mm * 14 mm

The Bluetooth communication between the microcomputer and the mobile application is HTTP-LIKE and will be based on data stream exchanges through proper network sockets.

Being HTTP-LIKE, among the Bluetooth connection, the two peers are in a client-server configuration where the microcomputer act as the server and the mobile application as the client.

Acting as a Server, the microcontroller exposes APIs the mobile client will integrate to control engines or to get real-time sensors' data.

On the other side, the connection between the microcomputer and the rest of the mobile controller unit hardware is among the GPIO interface and is manned by a set of drivers. Each driver manages the low-level access between the service layer and all the hardware interfaces.

1.5. Freewheel back-end component

The back-end is an MVC application based on Symfony 4 framework with rest bundle installed to simplify the rest API service layer development. The back-end application stores all system and domain data in a MySQL database. All data is encrypted in transit and at rest respecting the GDPR requirements. Payment methods data, if needed, will be managed by PCI-DSS compliant third party acquirers. The back-end component exposes a set of APIs among the HTTPS communication layer, these APIs are organized in functional subset above a set of access levels outlined by a user-role configuration. In the communication with the mobile app context, service authorization respects OAuth2.0 protocol and so the back-end component expects a token that ensures data integrity. Server to server communication security with third party services could be enforced using mutual certificate exchange if needed. Service authorization flow includes the following steps:

1. The client prompts the user to enter their credentials (for instance, a username/password combination).
2. The client sends the credentials and its own identity to the authorization server.
3. The authorization server validates the information, then returns an access token and optionally a refresh token.
4. The client uses the access token to access resources on the resource server.

The access token will be valid until his expiration, the client can ask the authorization server a new one sending the related refresh token.

The mobile app client can optionally store a user's refresh token to avoid explicit authorization using credentials on the following uses. Storing a refresh token instead of user's credential and the possibility to invalidate a refresh token generating a new one is one of the best OAuth2.0 advantages in terms of security: in case of device stealing, the refresh token is the only violable information and it can be invalidated for a new one from another device.

1.6. FreeWheel engineering platform

The FreeWheel engineering platform is the component responsible for collecting and managing wheelchair models' data (tech specs, images, 3D models...) needed to build module adaptors. The FreeWheel engineering platform is a standalone integrated service component. The platform's application layer is based on Symfony MVC framework and exposes a set of APIs among a service layer the back-end component integrates. All data is stored in a dedicated MySQL database and is continuously kept up-to-date by platform operators through a back-office interface.

Alike every part inside the architecture, the FreeWheel engineering platform communicates with other components, among a cloud infrastructure over public web, through secure HTTPS over TLS connections. At the same time, services access authorization is ensured by OAuth2.0.

1.7. Maps engine and other third-party services

Cartography services are served by google maps API to the mobile application and the back-end component. Cartography services are needed for user geolocating and paths evaluating during the driving experience or locating racks. Alike other third party services, the maps engine is integrated with any other served part according to its interface control document and securing the communication between parts with OAuth2.0 authorization and HTTPS over TLS connections.

1.8. Design and Development Approach

The software life cycle model describes phases of the software cycle and the order in which those phases are executed. Each phase produces deliverables required by the next phase in the life cycle. Requirements are translated into design. Code is produced according to the design which is called the development phase. After coding and development, the testing verifies the deliverable of the implementation phase against requirements.

Requirement gathering and analysis: Business requirements are gathered in this phase. This phase is the main focus of the project managers and stakeholders. Meetings with managers, stakeholders, and users are held in order to determine the requirements like; Who is going to use the system? How will they use the system? What data should be input into the system? What data should be output by the

system? These are general questions that get answered during the requirements gathering phase. After requirement gathering, these requirements are analyzed for their validity and the possibility of incorporating the requirements in the system to be development is also studied. Finally, a Requirement Specification document is created which serves the purpose of guideline for the next phase of the model.

The testing team follows the Software Testing Life Cycle and starts the Test Planning phase after the requirements analysis is completed.

Design: In this phase, the system and software design are prepared from the requirement specifications which were studied in the first phase. System Design helps in specifying hardware and system requirements and also helps in defining overall system architecture. The system design specifications serve as input for the next phase of the model. In this phase, the testers come up with the Test strategy, where they mention what to test, how to test.

Examples of studies on the experience

Implementation / Coding: On receiving system design documents, the work is divided in modules/units and actual coding is started. Since in this phase the code is produced so it is the main focus for the developer. This is the longest phase of the software development life cycle.

Testing: After the code is developed it is tested against the requirements to make sure that the product is actually solving the needs addressed and gathered during the requirements phase. During this phase,

all types of functional testing like unit testing, integration testing, system testing, acceptance testing are done as well as non-functional testing are also done.

Deployment: After successful testing, the product is delivered/deployed to the Customer for their use. As soon as the product is given to the Customers they will first do the beta testing. If any changes are required or if any bugs are caught, then they will report it to the engineering team. Once those changes are made or the bugs are fixed then the final deployment will happen.

Maintenance: Once when the Customers start using the developed system then the actual problems come up and need to be solved from time to time. This process where the care is taken for the developed product is known as maintenance.

1.9. Software quality assurance

Software Quality Assurance (SQA) has been done by a specialized third-party company and it is the set of activities that ensure processes, procedures, as well as standards suitable for the project, are implemented correctly.

Software Quality Assurance is a process that is done iteratively during the SDLC test phase. It focuses on improving the process of development of software so that problems can be prevented before they become a major issue. Software Quality Assurance is a kind of activity that is applied throughout the software process.

Software Quality Assurance has:

1. A quality management approach
2. Formal technical reviews
3. Multi testing strategy
4. Effective software engineering technology
5. Measurement and reporting mechanism

During the FreeWheel software lifecycle, the following software quality assurance activities have been done and, at the same time, they compose the SLDC test phase:

1. **SQA Management Plan:**

Make a plan how you will carry out the SQA throughout the project. Think about which set of software engineering activities are the best for the project.

2. **Set The Check Points:**

SQA team sets checkpoints and evaluates the performance of the project on the basis of collected data on different checkpoints.

3. **Measure Change Impact:**

The changes for making the correction of an error sometimes reintroduce more errors keeps the measure of the impact of change on the project. In this case, the SQA evaluates the compatibility of this fix with the whole project.

4. **Issue list propagation:**

At the end of each iteration, all issues are sent to the development team in order to integrate all fixes.

2. Mobile App and FreeWheel Service

2.1. General description

The mobile application is the touchpoint that the Customer access to unlock the whole service experience. The App features set covers all the Customer experience's phases described in the Service Blueprint (D4.2): gearing up (service suitability check, registration, assistance to adaptor design, production delivery and installation), booking (in advance or on-the-fly), running service (identifying, attaching, and detaching the module) and wrapping up (detaching the module, paying).

2.2. Experience and Features Comprehension

Before starting the textual explanation in the next chapter, a set of guidelines and keywords is going to be clarified in order to simplify the reading and comprehension of the application journey described in chapter 2.3 "In-App service experience and functionalities".

2.2.1. Reading guidelines and Legend

The pictures that are going to be shown are screens taken from the application. They are going to be described by the text on the side. Here a complete legend of what you can find in the side text of each following picture:

- *Italic blue text*: Informative text, placeholders and in general every non-interactive text is present in the screens.
- Underlined blue text: menu voices and textual links.
- **Bold blue text**: it refers to buttons, text fields and any interactive element of the interface.

And an example of the legend applied to a screen:

Back Arrow button to get at the previous state

Navigation is the name of the feature enabled

Chatbot button to open the chatbot interface

Destination label that shows where the Customer is headed

Module and navigation status indicators (battery level, speed, distance)

Rental Closing button it shows the information to close the rental

Manual Control activation button enables manual driving joystick while in navigation mode

Autonomous Drive activation indicator

Accompanying mode switch to enable/disable this specific mode

Point of interest access button, by swiping up you can access the POIs list

2.2.2. Glossary

1. **Customers:** is the users' category that groups the clients accessing the service.
2. **Employees:** everyone is working within the FreeWheel service to make it happen.
3. **Rack Operators:** a category of employees working at the rack to assist service operations.
4. **Remote Support:** team and processes that support the user via the app in case of issues.
5. **Chatbot:** the main *remote support* tool to offer immediate help and information to the Customer. It is a computer program designed to simulate conversation with human users, that is able to comprehend questions written via a chat interface (so very familiar nowadays) and actively support the user in choices and understanding. Ultimately it is used to have the Customer talking to a real operator to solve any issue that it is beyond its handling.
6. **Frontend:** everything is happening in front of the Customer, in the mobile app case, everything is shown on the screen of the smartphone and every process happens in front of his/her eyes. From a service perspective, this includes also operations and actions performed by employees and everyone connected to the experience.
7. **Interface:** is the complex of information and features that enables the communication between the software and the Customer.
8. **Screen:** is what the application is showing in an exact moment to the Customer in the *interface*. Each one of the following pictures, that are going to help the explanation, are screens of the application.
9. **Status:** is each configuration of the *interface* that is in place to answer different inputs both from the Customer and from the software. A specific step of the experience could have different *statuses*, that are generating different *screens*.

10. **Backend:** side operations, algorithms, processes, and employees actions that are happening “behind the screen” of the smartphone, triggered by *front-end* inputs or not (i.e.: when the Customer complete registration, a new record is created in the database).

2.3. In-App service experience and functionalities

In this section, the document explains the journey that a Customer follows in accessing FreeWheel service, from registration to paying the first rent, explaining the interactions with the app and how it works to make the service happen within the FreeWheel ecosystem.

2.3.1. App Launch

Once installed the app can be launched on the Customer’s smartphone.

Description and Interaction: FreeWheel logo is shown. The Customer launch the app then has to wait for the app loading. He/she is aware of what is happening on the screen, cannot interact or influence the operation excepting by closing the app with standard Android procedure. The application establishes TCP communication with the backend to authenticate the user/Customer and enable the service.

2.3.2. Login

The screenshot shows the login page for 'freewheel'. At the top left is the 'freewheel' logo. Below it, the text 'Welcome sign in' is displayed. There are two input fields: 'Email' with the value 'freewheel@' and 'Password'. Below the password field is a link 'Recover your password'. At the bottom, there is a link 'If you don't have an account [Register](#)' and a blue 'Login' button.

Now the application needs to authenticate the user (Customer) via a classic username and password request.

Screen Description: login page where Customers can input username and password with a **dedicated input field** and **log in** (for already registered Customers), [recover the password](#) if forgotten or [register a new account](#). The last one is the case for new Customers approaching the service.

The app checks email and password matching with existent combinations, can give back an error message in case of wrong credentials and encourage password recovery.

A new registration is going to record in the database the data for a new Customer if the registration process goes straight.

2.3.3. Registration: Service Accessibility Check

The first step of the registration process is the accessibility check. This happens mainly via a Chatbot interface (described in the glossary). This step is mandatory, FreeWheel service has specific requirements as described in the WP2, so before allowing everyone to register, to avoid frustration we are using this step to assess the accessibility.

Screen Description: chat interface with a **chat input field**. The chatbot asks to describe the Customer's disability and interact with him or her in order to retrieve information. Behind the chatbot suitability evaluation, there is a heuristic keyword search-based algorithm. The algorithm scans the whole text the user write describing his motion limitation and evaluate the probability his condition can match one of the cases in the set of positives. In case of a positive match, the user will not proceed with the onboarding.

We are sorry, what you've written about you suggests that FreeWheel is still not safe and suitable enough to give you a commensurate experience quality.

Contact us

If the chatbot software assesses that the potential Customer cannot access the service, it informs clearly the Customer, leaving the chance to contact and talk to a FreeWheel employee.

Screen Description: chatbot message and **Contact button** to access support contact details.

2.3.4. Registration: Credentials definition

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for registration. At the top, the time is 1:47, and there are icons for signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery. Below the status bar, there is a menu icon on the left, the title 'Access data' in the center, and a chatbot icon on the right. The form consists of three input fields: 'Email' (containing 'freewheel@'), 'Password', and 'Confirm password'. Below the 'Password' field is a 'Password Strength' indicator, which is a horizontal bar with a red-to-blue gradient. At the bottom of the screen is a blue bar with the text 'Next'.

If the chatbot assesses the suitability of the service, the registration process starts with credentials creation.

Description and Interaction: At the top left of the screen the **Menu button**, the *title of the screen*, and the **chatbot button** to request help, to request help. Follow the *Access data* form with **email** and **password input fields**, with password confirmation step, and **next button**. The Customer must fill the form to proceed with the registration. The app collects information in the new Customer record in the backend.

2.3.5. Registration: Personal data

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for a registration form titled "Personal data". At the top left, there is a back arrow button. The form contains the following fields and options:

- Name:** A single-line text input field.
- Surname:** A single-line text input field.
- Gender:** Two radio buttons labeled "Male" (selected) and "Female".
- Birth date:** A date picker input field.
- City:** A single-line text input field.
- State of Birth:** A single-line text input field.
- Country:** A single-line text input field.
- Tax code:** A single-line text input field.

At the bottom of the screen, there is a prominent blue button labeled "Next".

Registration continues with the personal data form.

Screen Description: at the top of the page, since we are in a process, the menu button is replaced by an **arrow button** that acts as “back” to get back to the previous section. Below the **form** collects basic personal data. The Customer must fill the form to proceed with the registration, he/she can ask for help via chatbot if needed. The app collects information in the new Customer record in the backend.

2.3.6. Registration: Address data

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for the 'Address data' registration step. At the top, the time is 1:47, and there are icons for signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery. Below the status bar, there is a back arrow on the left, the title 'Address data' in the center, and a chatbot icon on the right. The form consists of four input fields, each with a label above it: 'Address', 'City', 'Country', and 'Postal code'. The 'Address' field is the largest, followed by 'City' and 'Country', and 'Postal code' is the smallest. At the bottom of the screen, there is a solid blue bar with the word 'Next' in white text.

Registration continues with the address data form.

Description and Interaction: nothing changes at the top of the page, now the form collects *address data*. The Customer must fill the form to proceed with the registration, he/she can ask for help via chatbot if needed. The app collects information in the new Customer record in the backend.

2.3.7. Registration: Terms & Conditions acceptance

As every service, even FreeWheel is supposed to have terms and conditions, in this screen, there is only a placeholder text since no terms and conditions are defined at this stage.

Description and Interaction: the top of the page remains unchanged, below terms and conditions in a text form. The Customer has to scroll down the text to read it and use the **Register button** at the end to confirm acceptance.

2.3.8. Registration: Email verification

Standard email verification step, the Customer receives a link via email and by clicking it confirms the email used during registration

Description and Interaction: The top of the page remains the same, *info text* to explain the step. In the end, a link to have a new email sent, in case the first is lost. The Customer has to check hisorher email account to retrieve the link and then proceed to the next step.

2.3.9. Registration: Payment data

The screenshot shows a mobile application interface for entering payment data. At the top, the status bar shows the time 1:47, signal strength, Wi-Fi, and battery icons. The app title is 'Payment Data'. Below the title are five input fields: 'Card number', 'Card's owner', 'Exp month', 'Exp year', and 'CW'. A link 'Skip, I'll do it later' is positioned below the 'CW' field. At the bottom of the screen is a large blue button labeled 'Continue'.

To handle the future pay-per-use payment of the service, a credit card is needed, the data are stored in a safe way.

Description and Interaction: Top of the page remains unchanged, follows a **standard form** to collect credit card data, the Customer has to fill in the credit card data, data are checked to ensure validity, and if they are, stored safely and associated to the Customer account that can **continue** the process.

By **skipping** the step, he/she will be prompted again later to add this information.

2.3.10. Registration: Wheelchair identification

1:47

← Wheelchair identification

Please, select your wheelchair's manufacturer and model

Manufacturer

Meyra

Model

ZX1 1.360

[My wheelchair is not in the list](#)

Continue

This step is where the experience starts to be really customized on the FreeWheel service. In order to fully access the service the Customer needs an adaptor to be installed. To produce it the Customer's wheelchair has to be identified correctly.

Description and Interaction: Top of the screen unchanged. Below 2 **dropdown list selectors** to choose manufacturer and model of the wheelchair. Below a preview of the wheelchair is going to be presented to the Customer, retrieved from the FreeWheel Platform database. At the end of the page, if the Customer identified and recognized his/her wheelchair can **continue**, otherwise can flag the service that [the wheelchair is not in the list](#).

2.3.11. Registration: Wheelchair details

1:47

← Additional Wheelchair Details

We already have your wheelchair in our database!

Since we are going to produce an adaptor to make you able to use FreeWheel service, we are going to ask you a few more details before starting the production.

Manufacturer

Meyra

Model

ZX1 1.360

Web page link

Does your wheelchair have any major modification?
Custom wheels, framework changes, etc...

Yes No

Not all the wheelchairs, even if the same model, are identical, due to customizations that users can need or request. So if the Customer finds the wheelchair in the database, in this step, he/she can provide specific details. They are not all requested, but it is strongly suggested to provide them to ensure the correct production of the adaptor performed by the engineering team.

Description and Interaction: the Customer finds **manufacturer** and **model fields** already filled in from the previous step, he/she can provide a **web page link** to the manufacturer website or an online video. Then, since the adaptor takes advantage of the wheelchair's frame and it is important to check wheels size, a direct question is asked, and the Customer must answer yes or no with a **radio button** choice ("No" by default).

Please provide some pictures of the wheelchair paying attention to have clear images of:

- Wheels
- Framework behind and below the seat

And pictures of the modifications described above, if any.

Please take also pictures of any documentation you can retrieve that can help our employees to identify correctly your wheelchair.

- Specs sheets
- Packaging
- Instructions manual

Continue

In case of a “No”, the Customer can scroll down to the section dedicated to adding pictures. The *text* explains what kind of pictures the Customer should add to help the employees to be sure the adaptor fits perfectly. then he/she can **continue**.

Does your wheelchair have any major modification?
Custom wheels, framework changes, etc...

Yes No

Please describe the modifications. In case of custom wheels please add manufacturer and model in the description.

*Required

In case of a "Yes" to the question about customizations, a new **text field** appears and is required, to collect information coming directly from the Customer and enrich the details for the engineering team.

All the information is recorded in the backend and associated with the Customer profile to produce the adaptor and ship it.

2.3.12. Registration: New Wheelchair

1:47

← New Wheelchair

Your wheelchair is not in our database yet.

Please provide some data about so we can design a brand new adaptor for your wheelchair and make the FreeWheel service available to you.

Manufacturer

Required

Model

Required

Web page link

Does your wheelchair have any major modification?
Custom wheels, framework changes, etc...

Yes No

In case the wheelchair is not in the database, and the Customer selects the option, a new interface, practically the same as the one described in the previous step, with the only exception of the *title*, and the requested **fields for manufacturer and model**. All this information is going to be recorded in the backend and made available for the engineering team.

2.3.13. Registration: Wheelchair preview

If the Customer finds his or her wheelchair, the app could be able, according to what is available in the FreeWheel Platform, to show a preview of the wheelchair while running the service, with adaptor and module installed.

Description and Interaction: the Customer can look at the preview, if available, and then **continue**.

2.3.14. Registration: FreeWheel point selection

The service experience expects a meeting to install the adaptor on the Customer's wheelchair and train him or her to access properly the service. So now he/she has to select a FreeWheel point where employees deliver this part of the service. This spot is going to be the final destination of the produced adaptor, that is why is mandatory to select it now.

Description and Interaction: the Customer can scroll the **selectable list** or use the **search input field** to look for FreeWheel points near to a specific address. Once selected and recorded the information, the app will move to the next step, which is the conclusion of this registration process.

2.3.15. Registration: Confirmation

The registration process is now finished. A confirmation is displayed for the Customer.

Description and Interaction: The screen contains some *text that informs the Customer about the next steps* of the process. It also encourages to use the **shipment status button** to follow the process.

2.3.16. Registration: Adaptor production status

The first step is the production of a new adaptor, that is happening with the work of the engineering team. They access to all the information about the wheelchair collected during the registration, they can also get back to the Customer via email to request additional information and ensure a better result. The application does not let the Customer access the service until this process and the installation and training appointment happen.

Description and Interaction: the app is now locked in this status, the interface at the top shows the **menu button**, the *title*, and the **chatbot button**. The Customer access in every moment the information and can check it, for any question or issue (like changing the FreeWheel point, if possible) he/she can use the **chatbot**. This information is managed via backend, where service-related personnel will update the status displayed accordingly to the production advancements.

When the adaptor is produced and sent to the FreeWheel point, the application will display the information and update the date of arrival if needed.

Description and Interaction: the interface is almost identical to the previous, the Customer can still use the [chatbot](#) to request help or additional information.

The adaptor is shipped, to the selected FreeWheel point, the app is still locked but shows clearly the information to the Customer.

Description and Interaction: the screen display the information and encourage the user to **book the appointment** for installation and training.

2.3.17. Registration: Installation and Training appointment booking

This is the beginning of a short booking process to choose the date and time for the installation and training appointment.

Description and Interaction: at the top left of the interface, the menu button is replaced by a **back arrow button** since we entered a new procedure. The *text* explains details about the meeting and explains that after this, the Customer will be able to use all service features. At the bottom, a **button**, allow proceeding.

In this step, the Customer selects a day available for the designated FreeWheel point.

Description and Interaction: The **date picker** is a spinner that allows to fastly move in the near future to select a day, the availability is synchronized via backend with availabilities of the FreeWheel point. Once highlighted the desired day, using the **arrow button** at the bottom right the Customer can proceed.

Now the Customer has to select an available time for the appointment.

Description and Interaction: the **picker** now shows available times for the appointment, again is a spinner, to give consistency to the interface. At the bottom of the page, the **date selected** in the previous step is clearly visible, near to the **arrow button** to move forward in the procedure.

The booking process ends now, the application is again locked in a waiting status. At the installation and training appointment, a technician will install the customized adaptor on the Customer wheelchair, soon after he/she will be trained on service operations, from booking to driving, to close the first rental and manage emergency situations and safety during use. Once the meeting happens, the Customer is able to use the service properly, a FreeWheel employee will change his/her status as Customer to "active" in the application backend and he/she will be able to access all the features.

Description and Interaction: the top of the screen shows the **menu button** again, the *info text* explains about the appointment and shows all the important data to reach the FreeWheel point. At the bottom an **"Add to calendar" button** allows the Customer to add all the details to a calendar event on an external app, such as Google Calendar.

2.3.18. Homepage

The application is now unlocked and ready for the core experience of the service. Starting from the homepage presented, the Customer can now book a module in advance or on-the-fly.

Description and Interaction: the top of the page presents the **menu button**, followed by an **input field** to look for FreeWheel points searching addresses or names. The **chatbot** remains available. Below the Customer is localized on the map via the smartphone GPS and shows FreeWheel points nearby, selecting one of them the booking process begins. The **Instant Booking button** allows a Customer near to a FreeWheel point to instantly collect a module, and activate the QRCode scanner (chapter 2.3.23 of this document).

At the bottom of the page the [list of FreeWheel points](#) can be accessed and searched via the **search field**.

2.3.19. Menu

This screen wants to show the app main menu, where the Customer can always access important information.

Description and Interaction: the menu slides from the left when the **menu button** is pressed, after the *logo* and the *welcome*, the menu voices are:

- [Bookings](#): to retrieve bookings made in advance
- [Settings](#): to explore app settings
- [Profile](#): to explore the Customer's profile
- [Logout](#)

2.3.20. Booking: FreeWheel point selection from list

To start a booking process the Customer must select a FreeWheel point. He/she can select it from the map or from the list.

Description and Interaction: The screen presents the list of [FreeWheel points](#) that can be searched using the **input field**, to start a booking process.

2.3.21. Booking: Date and Time selection

Once selected a FreeWheel point a date and time booking process starts.

Description and Interaction: the top of the page shows the **back arrow button** since the Customer entered a process. Below the *FreeWheel point is re-proposed*, right under that a **big round button** suggests to pick the date for the booking.

The date picker allows selecting a date. Modules' availability in the selected FreeWheel point is managed by an algorithm that monitors, availability, battery level and all the bookings placed in the system.

Description and Interaction: the **spinner** allows to select available dates, once highlighted, using the **arrow button** the Customer moves to the next step.

Once the Customer selected a day, the algorithm proposes a list of times available for the selected day.

Description and Interaction: **spinner selector with times** is used to select a suitable time, once highlighted the Customer can confirm with the **arrow button**.

The booking is now resumed before confirmation.

Description and Interaction: at the top of the page, a **back arrow button** allows the Customer to exit from the booking process, below he/she can review the *data* and if necessary edit them by pressing the **button inside** the blue circle. If the data are fine can be **confirmed at the bottom of the page**.

2.3.22. Booking: Confirmation and Summary

If the booking data are validated by the algorithm the booking is confirmed and a confirmation is displayed. This confirmation can always be retrieved from the booking section among the menu's voices.

Description and Interaction: at the top of the page an **arrow button** brings the user back to the homepage while below the reservation is resumed with all the information for the rental. The **check-in button** is needed at the designated time to start the rental.

2.3.23. Rack Identification

The rack identification step allows avoiding issues related to the start of the booking, only when arrived at the rack the rent can really start. The Customer lands directly here when using the **instant booking** option from the app homepage.

Description and Interaction: the app uses the camera to scan the QRCode of the rack and ensure that the booking starts correctly. The Customer can always get **back** to the booking to check data.

2.3.24. Module Identification

Recognizing a rack via QRCode allows the app to identify the FreeWheel point, matching it with booking needs, the algorithm can choose the most suitable module for the Customer. At this stage, the rack operator enters the scene to support the Customer with the installation of the module.

Description and Interaction: the **back arrow button** interrupts the check-in and cancels the module booking. All the *data are resumed*, so if everything appears correct the Customer can move to the next step with the **“Continue” button**.

2.3.25. Security Check

A security check with the personal PIN, received during the registration via SMS, is requested to allow the start of the rental.

Description and Interaction: at the top of the page, the **back arrow button** is available to get back to the booking review, while the **chatbot button** is available for support, even if the Customer is supposed to be at the rack having the help of the rack operator. If the PIN is valid the Customer is authenticated and moves to the installation.

2.3.26. Module Installation

The Customer now is having the module installed by the rack operator, he/she is supposed to wait in position at the rack while the operator put in place the module on the adaptor, previously installed. During this operation, the rental is not yet started, so the Customer is not paying.

Description and Interaction: at this moment the Customer must wait for the rack operator that is installing the module, so the employee can give the confirmation to the system and the rental can begin.

2.3.27. Manual Drive

The rental starts, the Customer can manually control the module to have a smooth and safe start, is to be remembered that he/she was already trained during the installation and training appointment.

Description and Interaction: since the rental begins the app is locked in the driving status, the menu is no longer available, in order to avoid that the Customer could perform some unwanted operation (i.e.: a logout), the **chatbot** is available for any question or issue. The Customer can clearly identify the status, reading the *screen title "Controller"*, below *information about battery level and speed*. The map indicates the position of the Customer in the location, a **rental closing button** shows related information, while the **digital controller** allows the Customer to drive the module around. The **Points of interest list** can be swiped up to select a navigable point.

2.3.28. Point of Interest selection

The point of interest list is a list of mapped places in the location that the Customer can navigate to using the manual or autonomous driving.

Description and Interaction: swiping up, the list can be scrolled or searched with the **input field**, once identified it can be selected tapping on it. This is going to trigger the calculation of a route by the FreeWheel system. To exit the list without selecting a destination, swiping down the list is sufficient.

2.3.29. Navigation: Manual Drive

Once the route is calculated, it is displayed on the map and allows the Customer to manually or autonomously drive to it, continuing the experience accessing to one of the service core features.

Description and Interaction: activating the navigation a **back arrow button** appears at the top left of the interface, the *title* changes to identify the feature and the **chatbot** remains available. Right under the *navigation's destination* is remarked and together with the *battery percentage* and *speed, distance from the destination* is shown. Now the map shows also the route tracked, to be followed by the Customer using the usual **digital controller**, or switching to autonomous driving mode tapping on the **auto button** at the top right of the map.

2.3.30. Navigation: Autonomous Drive and Accompanying Mode

The autonomous driving mode when activated will immediately follow the route using the sensors and the algorithms implemented, to avoid obstacles and reach destination.

Description and Interaction: In the *navigation* mode with autonomous driving enabled, at the bottom of the map it is clearly indicated in a *dedicated box*, where is also present the **accompanying mode switch**.

The Accompanying person mode could be activated if the Customer is moving with other people (such as friends or partners), to properly set the module sensing system and the algorithm to not consider nearest people as obstacles.

2.3.31. Navigation: New Point of Interest selection

During the navigation the Point of Interests are still available to change the destination if needed.

Description and Interaction: at the top of the page the **back arrow button** allows to exit the *navigation* feature indicated in the center, followed by the **chatbot button**. The interaction with the list is the same described at 2.3.28.

2.3.32. Bluetooth Connection Unavailable

If the Bluetooth connection between the module and mobile app breaks the Customer is warned and encouraged to use the physical joystick. Meanwhile, the app will try to reconnect to the module, if it succeeds the app will be back to work normally and all the features available. The Customer knows this eventuality from the training.

Description and Interaction: The dialogue box appears when the mobile app notices the Bluetooth connection interruption. It remains on the screen until the communication is established back, offers the [link to request help via chatbot](#) and the **button** to activate the joystick.

2.3.33. Rental Closure

The screenshot shows a white dialog box with a blue border. At the top left is a blue lowercase 'i' icon. The main text is in blue and reads: "Please reach the nearest rack and an operator will provide rental closure operations." Below this, it says "If you are experiencing problems, [let us help](#)." At the bottom left, it says "Thanks". At the bottom of the dialog box is a solid blue bar with the white text "Close this message".

The Customer knows from the initial training that a rental can be closed only to a FreeWheel point. The info explains this procedure again.

Description and Interaction: the **info button** on the map claims the dialogue box with the info text and the [link](#) to request help via chatbot. At the bottom a **close button**.

2.3.34.

After the rental closure operations, the Customer will automatically receive a receipt that resumes all the information and the final price of the rental.

Description and Interaction: the dialogue box shows all the information and the **close button** that brings the Customer back to the homepage.

Conclusions

This deliverable is closing the WP4 “FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design”, following the service design process that led the whole work package, the consortium was able to align developments running through WPS, from hardware to software, to achieve a common understanding of desired project’s outcome.

The Mobile App is only a part of the FreeWheel system that is going to be demonstrated in the final pilot of the project, but it gives a good taste of how the service intends to work from a Customer perspective. This document also wants to help to have a wider understanding of all operations and side processes that are required to deliver the experience, by confirming and updating the journey described in the Service Blueprint (D4.2). Now the aim of the app is to be smoothly integrated with all the other solutions still developing in running WPs, as forecasted in the service ideation and design.

It is to be remarked that what is delivered today is a fully working prototype that works in the frame of the service designed so far. The application is going to be additionally tested many times in the FreeWheel system from now to the end of the project and fine-tuned, especially regard to the communication with module and driving, in order to obtain a better experience for the demonstrator.

Next Steps

From now on the efforts are going to concentrate on constantly aligning the consortium to the agreed service design in an iterative approach, as previously described, analyzing all the solutions implemented in the framework of the designed experience for the final demonstrator, as well as keeping an eye on the possibilities highlighted for the hypothetic full implementation (as mentioned in the deliverable 4.2 “Service Implementation Roadmap”). This is going to create room for enhancements in the final experience, thanks to the collaboration between all the partners that made possible all the WP4s work, with co-design activities and frequent collaborative work, that are going to continue till the end of the FreeWheel project.